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CONTENT ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL REPRESENTATION IN THE NARRATIVES OF CHRONICALLY ILL PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the article analyzed: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the content expressed. This construction of discourse permeates the entire process of human communication and is developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the discourse emanating from the subject. Objective: To analyze the content of textual fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation. Methodology: Qualitative research. In order to treat the material, we opted for Bardin’s (1977) content analysis method, which analyses the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way, as described by Minayo (2000), who organizes it into three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the results obtained and interpretation under the reference of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009). Final Considerations: In the analysis of the study, we found two distinct processes in the discourse, confirming our hypothesis that the attitude is influenced by everyday experiences. The study shows objectification and anchoring, analyzed on the basis of TRS, which demonstrates the influential role of everyday experiences and the transformation of the subjective into objective through the hierarchization of responsibility for one’s reality.